

Studies on Complex Formation between Vanadic Acid (V^{5+}) and α -Hydroxy Acids

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The reaction between vanadic acid and α -hydroxy acids results in the formation of complexes which undergo slow reduction. In this respect vanadic acid resembles tungstic, molybdic, antimonio acids, etc, which also form such complexes, but mostly of very stable type. With tartaric, citric, mandelic, and lactic acids, the respective composition of the complexes of vanadic acid has been found to be 1:2, 1:1, 1:2, and 1:2. Job's method¹ of continued variation has been adopted to determine the composition of the complexes. The kinetics of the formation of the complexes has also been studied.

Complex formation, involving metallic acid oxides and α -hydroxy acids, is well known². Different physico-chemical methods have been adopted to ascertain the nature of these complexes. Clark³, Richardson⁴, Gate and Richardson⁵, and others have prepared solutions of germanic, molybdic, tungstic, and antimonio acids by ion-exchange method and have studied the formation of their complexes with α -hydroxy acids by recording the variation of conductance and pH with the mole fraction of the metallic acids. In this connection, the complex formation of niobic and tantalio acids with α -hydroxy acids, studied by Fairbrother and Taylor⁶, of molybdic acid with tartaric acid by Biswas⁷, arsenio acid with tartaric acid by Britton and Jackson⁸, and sodium tungstate and sodium molybdate with tartaric acid by Banerjee and Bhattacharya⁹ may be mentioned. From polarographic characteristics Lingane¹⁰ and Lingane and Meites¹¹ have presented evidence for the existence of complexes of vanadium at different oxidation states with several complexing agents including tetravalent vanadium with tartrate, citrate, and oxalate ions respectively.

In the present communication, the results of investigation on complex formation between vanadic acid (V^{5+}) and several α -hydroxy acids by conductance measurements are recorded.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Ammonium metavanadate and α -hydroxy acid used were of A.R. quality, E. Merck. The resin used was Amberlite IR-120(H) of Rohm and Haas Company, Pennsylvania.

All conductance measurements were made at 25°, using a Philips conductivity measuring bridge, PR-9500, operating in the most sensitive range at 1000 C/S and a cell of constant 0.443.

Preparation of Vanadic Acid and its Estimation.—Moist resin (15 g.), previously washed with double-distilled water, was found to neutralise a normal alkali solution (30 ml). Using a known quantity of the resin, a column was prepared in a tall (about 30 cm) Pyrex glass tube on a bed of glass wool (E. Merck). The resin in the column was then washed repeatedly with conductivity water till the wash-water recorded the same conductance as that of the original conductivity water. The moist resin was made free of water as far as possible by suction. The ammonium metavanadate solution was then percolated through the resin column at a slow rate (2 drops per sec.), the amount in ml percolated being one-third of the total exchange capacity of the resin in order to achieve complete conversion. The yellow vanadic acid solution, thus obtained, was collected in a Jena bottle. Vanadic acid, thus prepared, was analysed for ammonia by Kjeldahl's method. As no ammonia was found, the acid prepared may be considered as quite pure. The concentration of the acid in the solution was determined by evaporating and heating to a constant weight a definite volume of the acid solution in a porcelain crucible. By maintaining more or less the same condition, vanadic acid of almost equal strength can always be prepared.

Preparation of the α -Hydroxy Acids.—The α -hydroxy acids were taken in separate measuring flasks and dissolved in conductivity water; their concentrations were determined by titration against a standard NaOH solution.

Properties of Vanadic Acid Prepared by Ion-exchange Method.—Like the other complex acids, viz., tungstic acid, silicic acid, antimonie acid, etc., vanadic acid, prepared in the aforesaid manner, became polymerised whereupon its conductance diminished slowly with the transformation of the yellow colour to red. If the concentration of the acid is not much, this change in conductance is quite small. A 0.06 *M* (with respect to vanadium) solution of vanadic acid can be kept for more than 6 hours without any appreciable change in conductance and colour. Since our experiments for each α -hydroxy acid were complete within 4 hours and the concentration of the vanadic acid used was of maximum strength equaling 0.058 *M* (w.r.t. V), the effect of polymerisation on the variation of conductance was negligible (vide Table I).

TABLE I

Conc. of vanadic acid = 0.06 *M* (w.r.t. V).

Temp. = 25°.

Time.	Sp. conductance.	Time.	Sp. conductance.
*0 hr.	4.850 $\times 10^{-3}$ mho. cm ⁻¹	3 hrs.	4.650 $\times 10^{-3}$ mho. cm ⁻¹
‡	4.850 $\times 10^{-3}$	5	4.660 $\times 10^{-3}$
1	4.851 $\times 10^{-3}$	6	4.649 $\times 10^{-3}$
2	4.852 $\times 10^{-3}$	7‡	4.648 $\times 10^{-3}$

*Immediately after preparation of the acid.

Complex Formation between Vanadic Acid and α -Hydroxy Acids

When the various α -hydroxy acids are mixed with vanadic acid, the specific conductance of the mixture increases with time, indicating complex formation. This is exemplified in Fig. 1 and in Fig. 3. Curves 1, 2, 3, and 4 of Fig. 1 refer to citric, tartaric, mandelic, and lactic acid respectively, each at a ratio equal to 1:8 as vanadic acid: α -hydroxy acid. Curve 2 of Fig. 3 refers to the formation of complex between vanadic acid and citric acid at equimolecular proportion. It should be mentioned that the complexes formed are not very stable and the stability diminishes as the ratio of vanadic acid to α -hydroxy acid increases. Unless the vanadic acid is in considerable excess, the formation of the complex takes place with increasing conductance, attains a maximum value, which remains constant for sometime, and thereafter diminishes with the reduction of the vanadic acid. In Fig. 2 (curves 1 to 4) the maximum value of the specific conductance is plotted against mole fraction of each of the α -hydroxy acids used. In each case a maximum is obtained corresponding to the ratios of 2:1, 2:1, 1:1, and 2:1 of vanadic to the α -hydroxy acids, such as, tartaric, lactic, citric, and mandelic acid respectively. These ratios may be taken as the composition of the respective complexes.

FIG. 1

Kinetics of Complex Formation

It has already been stated that the specific conductance of the vanadic acid and of α -hydroxy acid mixtures increase, attain a maximum, remain constant for sometime, and then decrease. This variation of conductance has been utilised for the study of the kinetics of the reaction. The change of specific conductance with time has been shown in

Fig. 1 (curves 1-4) and Fig. 3 (curve 2). When the maximum conductance has been attained, we may assume that the rate of formation of the complex from the reactants is equal to the rate of its decomposition into the reactants, neglecting the reduction of the vanadic acid which is a slow process. Hence when the concentrations of the reactants are the same, for a bi-molecular reaction we can write

$$\frac{d(S_t - S_i)}{dt} = k(S_f - S_t)^2 - k'(S_t - S_i),$$

FIG. 2

where S_i , S_t , and S_f are the specific conductance at time equal to zero, t , and at equilibrium respectively; k and k' are the specific reaction rates corresponding to the formation of the complex and its decomposition into the reactants respectively. In the initial

stages the rate of decomposition of the complex into the reactants can be neglected and so we can write

$$\frac{d(S_t - S_i)}{dt} = k(S_t - S_i)^2.$$

On integration we get

$$\frac{1}{(S_t - S_i)} = kt + \frac{1}{(S_t - S_i)} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

So a plot of $1/(S_t - S_i)$ against t will be linear at the initial stages of the reaction only (vide Fig. 3, curve 1).

FIG. 3

When the α -hydroxy acid is in large excess (8 times), the reaction will obviously appear to be a monomolecular one and should be represented by the equation:

$$k'' = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{(S_t - S_i)}{(S_t - S_i)}.$$

On rearrangement we get

$$\log (S_t - S_i) = \log (S_t - S_i) - t \frac{k''}{2.303} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where k'' is the first order reaction velocity constant. In this case a plot of $\log (S_t - S_i)$ against t will yield a straight line (vide Fig. 4). In this figure, curves 1, 2, 3, and 4 refer to 1:8 mixtures of citric, tartaric, lactic, and mandelic acid respectively.

DISCUSSION

It is clear from Fig. 2 (curves 1-4) that vanadic acid forms complexes with tartaric, citric, mandelic, and lactic acids at the ratios of 2:1, 1:1, 2:1, and 2:1 respectively. It has been found that succinic acid has got no effect on the conductance of the vanadic acid when mixed in any proportion. This indicates that the hydroxyl group present in the α -hydroxy acid is essential for complex formation. This is also in agreement with the view

of Lingane and Meites¹² that the formation of the complex of V^{5+} is greatly influenced by presence of hydroxyl group in the complexing agent, for vanadium tends to co-ordinate preferentially with oxygen. Thus tartrate ion forms more stable complex than citrate ion and oxalate ion forms the least stable complex of the series¹². The structures of the complexes with the α -hydroxy acids used may then be formulated in the following manners:

1. Vanadic acid-tartaric acid complex (2:1).

2. Vanadic acid-citric acid complex (1:1).

(cf. Zr oxide- α -hydroxy acid complex¹³).

3. Vanadic acid-mandelic acid complex (2:1) and vanadic acid-lactic acid complex (2:1).

(where R=Me or Ph).

12. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1892.

13. Blair (Jr.), "The Chemistry of the Co-ordination Complexes", 1956, p. 467.

Of the four structures given above, those due to tartaric and citric acids differ from those of mandelic/tartaric acid in respect of the linking of the hydroxyl and carboxyl groups (attached to an α -carbon atom) either to one or to two vanadic acid molecules. It may also be mentioned that the tartaric acid complex possesses red colour, whereas the other three complexes are almost colorless.

In addition to conductance data, other evidence of complex formation has been obtained from polarimetric measurements of rotation of a mixture of vanadic acid and mandelic acid. The change of colour from yellow to red on mixing vanadic acid with tartaric acid has been observed. Spectrophotometric study of this reaction by applying Job's method of continued variation indicates the formation of 2:1 complex in agreement with that found from conductometric data. The results will be communicated shortly.

FIG. 4

From Fig. 3 (curve 1) it is found that the reaction between vanadic acid and citric acid (1:1 complex formation reaction) at their equimolecular mixture is a bimolecular one up to a certain interval of time. This is to be expected since the rate of reverse reaction, that is, the decomposition of the complex into the reactants, has been neglected. The bimolecular reaction velocity constant is 0.375 as calculated from the slope of the curve. Fig. 4 (curves 1-4) represents the apparent monomolecular reaction when the α -hydroxy acids are in excess. The specific reaction velocity constants, as calculated from the slopes of the curves for citric, tartaric, mandelic, and lactic acids, are 0.228, 0.085, 0.136, and 0.2165 respectively.

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